

Questionnaire ETMED-L : References for the validated instruments

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MCPIS: Macleod Clark Professional Identity Scale

Adams K, Hean S, Sturgis P, Clark JM. Investigating the factors influencing professional identity of first-year health and social care students. *Learn. Health Soc. Care* 2006;5:55–68.

NeuroQ: Neurophobia screening tool

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DiPCareQ: Deprivation in Primary Care Questionnaire

Vaucher P, Bischoff T, Diserens EA, Herzig L, Meystre-Agustoni G, Panese F, et al. Detecting and measuring deprivation in primary care: development, reliability and validity of a self-reported questionnaire: the DiPCare-Q. *BMJ Open* 2012;2:e000692.

QCAE: Questionnaire of Cognitive and Affective Empathy

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GERT-S: Geneva Emotion Recognition Test - Short Form

Schlegel K, Grandjean D, Scherer KR. Introducing the Geneva Emotion Recognition Test: An example of Rasch-based test development. *Psychol. Assess.* 2014;26:666–72.

JSPE-S: Jefferson Scale of Physician Empathy - Student Version

Hojat M, Mangione S, Nasca TJ, Cohen MJM, Gonnella JS, Erdmann JB, et al. The Jefferson Scale of Physician Empathy: Development and preliminary psychometric data. *Educ. Psychol. Meas.* 2001;61:349–65.

AMSP: Ability to Modify Self-Presentation of the Revised Self-Monitoring Scale

Lennox RD, Wolfe RN. Revision of the self-monitoring scale. *J. Pers. Soc. Psychol.* 1984;46:1349–64.

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CES-D: Center for Epidemiological Studies - Depression Scale

Radloff LS. The CES-D scale: A self-report depression scale for research in the general population. *Appl. Psychol. Meas.* 1977;1:385–401.

Morin AJS, Moullec G, Maïano C, Layet L, Just JL, Ninot G. Psychometric properties of the Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale (CES-D) in French clinical and nonclinical adults. *Rev. D'Épidémiologie Santé Publique* 2011;59:327–40.

BDI: Beck's Depression Inventory

Beck AT, Ward CH, Mendelson M, Mock J, Erbaugh J. An Inventory for measuring depression. *Arch. Gen. Psychiatry* 1961;4:561–71.

Bourque P, Beaudette D. Étude psychométrique du questionnaire de dépression de Beck auprès d'un échantillon d'étudiants universitaires francophones. [Psychometric study of the Beck Depression Inventory on a sample of French-speaking university students.]. *Can. J. Behav. Sci. Rev. Can. Sci. Comport.* 1982;14:211–8.

STAI-T: State-Trait Anxiety Inventory - Trait

Spielberger CD. *Manual for the State-trait Anxiety Inventory*. Palo Alto, CA: Consulting Psychologists Press; 1983.

Gauthier J, Bouchard S. Adaptation canadienne-française de la forme révisée du State–Trait Anxiety Inventory de Spielberger. [A French-Canadian adaptation of the revised version of Spielberger's State–Trait Anxiety Inventory.]. *Can. J. Behav. Sci. Rev. Can. Sci. Comport.* 1993;25:559–78.

MBI-SS: Maslach Burnout Inventory-Student Survey

Maslach C, Schaufeli WB, Leiter MP. Job Burnout. *Annu. Rev. Psychol.* 2001;52:397–422.

Faye-Dumanget C, Carré J, Le Borgne M, Boudoukha PAH. French validation of the Maslach Burnout Inventory-Student Survey (MBI-SS). *J. Eval. Clin. Pract.* 2017;23:1247–51.

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ASSIST: Alcohol, Smoking and Substance Involvement Screening Test

Humeniuk R, Ali R, Babor TF, Farrell M, Formigoni ML, Jittiwutikarn J, et al. Validation of the alcohol, smoking and substance involvement screening test (ASSIST). *Addiction* 2008;103:1039–47.

Smart drug section of the C-SURF questionnaire

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